

Ralstonia spp. induced septicemia in a traumatized dog

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Abstract

This paper reports a rare case of *Ralstonia* spp. induced septicemia in a traumatized dog. A four-month-old intact male non-descript pup was admitted to the intensive care unit with a history of an automobile accident about 8 hours before presentation. Clinical findings included an open wound on the right caudal abdominal region, bruising and ecchymosis of the ventral abdominal wall, pale mucous membranes, prolonged capillary refill time and weak peripheral pulses. Haematological parameters showed severe leukocytosis and neutrophilia. Serum biochemical results showed low levels of glucose and elevated levels of creatinine and alkaline phosphatase. On AFAST (Abdominal Focused Assessment using Sonography for Trauma) no free intra-abdominal fluid was identified. Radiographic findings include pelvis fracture. A whole blood sample was taken aseptically from the patient as the patient was clinically suspected of septic SIRS. The DNA was extracted from the blood and subjected to PCR using the universal 16S rRNA primer. The eluted PCR product was sequenced. The homology of the PCR product was checked by BLAST analysis with the sequences already available in the gene bank and *Ralstonia* spp. septicemia was identified. Treatment included intravenous fluid therapy, broad spectrum antibiotics, analgesics and supplemental oxygen. Despite of aggressive treatment animal collapsed after six hours of presentation. Our report describes a rare case of *Ralstonia* associated with sepsis in a traumatized dog and, to our knowledge, this case is the first identification of *Ralstonia* species from clinical samples of veterinary patients in India.

Keywords - Trauma, Dog, *Ralstonia* spp., SIRS, Sepsis.

Introduction:

The genus *Ralstonia* encompasses a group of non-fermentative, Gram-negative bacteria in moist environments, such as water, soil and plants. Three *Ralstonia* species viz., *R. pickettii*, *R. insidiosa* and *R. mannitolilytica*, formerly designated as *Burkholderia pickettii*, *B. solanacearum* and *Pseudomonas thomasii*,

respectively, have been recognized as opportunistic human pathogens (Ryan and Adley, 2014) and recently as commensals in dogs eyes (Torikachvili *et. al.*, 2024). Clinical conditions associated with *Ralstonia* spp. range from minor respiratory infections to severe invasive infections such as sepsis or meningitis (Ryan and Adley, 2013). *R. mannitolilytica* is

implicated in common sources of nosocomial outbreaks due to the addition of contaminated water to intravenous solutions (Gröbner *et al.*, 2007), oxygen-delivery devices (Jhung *et al.*, 2007) and humidifying respiratory therapy devices (Block *et al.*, 2013). Lucarelli *et al.* (2017) reported an outbreak due to *R. mannitolilytica* in oncology patients bearing a central venous catheter (CVC), and the authors also stated that the source of the outbreak could not be readily identified, and further investigations suggested that contaminated saline solution used for flushing CVC may have been the source of the outbreak. In canine patients

History and Observations

A four month old intact male non-descript pup weighing 13.6 kg was referred to the Critical Care Unit of the Madras Veterinary College Teaching Hospital with the history of auto mobile accident about 8 hours before presentation. At the time of presentation to the hospital the pup was on lateral recumbency and non-alert. The pup had a rectal temperature of 100.9°F, respiratory rate of 54 breaths per minute, tachycardia (236 beats per minute) and weak peripheral pulses. Physical examination revealed distended abdomen, pale conjunctival mucous membranes and prolonged capillary refill time. Open wound was observed on right caudal abdominal region. Bruising and ecchymosis of ventral abdominal wall (**Fig. 1**) was also observed. Severe pain evinced on palpation of abdomen.

Clinical Investigations:

Hematological findings include hemoglobin of 13.0 g/dl, packed cell volume of 32.8%, total erythrocyte count of 5.57 million cells per cu.mm, WBC Count of 46,000 per cu.mm and platelet count of 4,12,000 per cu.mm. On blood picture neutrophilia was noticed. Serum biochemical parameters include BUN- 28.58 mg/dL, Creatinine- 2.32 mg/ dL, Total Proteins- 4.70 g/ dL, Albumin-2.60g/ dL , ALT- 81 IU/ dL ,ALP-690 IU/ dL , Calcium- 12.75 mg/dL, Phosphorous- 8.98 mg/dL and Glucose- 38 mg/

dL. Pelvis fracture was diagnosed on ventro dorsal view (Pelvis-VD view) of radiographic examination. Emergency room ultrasonographic examination (AFAST) was performed on dorsal recumbency and findings include no free abdominal fluid (**Fig. 2**).

Treatment:

The dog was stabilized with crystalloid fluid therapy at the rate of 10ml per kg body weight and colloid therapy at the rate of 5ml per kg body weight. Supplemental oxygen was administered via oxygen hood (flow rate at 3 L/min). Hypoglycemia was treated with 5% Dextrose. Broad spectrum antibiotic therapy was given with combination of cefotaxime and metronidazole at the dose rate of 30 mg and 15 mg per kg body weight respectively. Analgesia was provided with butorphanol at the dose rate of 0.3 mg per kg body weight once in every 4 hours. Other treatments included ondansetron (0.4 mg/kg IV q 12 h) and pantoprazole (1 mg/kg IV q 24 h). Despite of aggressive treatment animal collapsed after six hours of presentation. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) was unsuccessful.

PCR and Sequencing Analysis:

In this case animal fulfilled three of the SIRS criteria (Respiratory Rate- 54 breaths per minute, Heart Rate- 236 beats per minute and WBC Count of 46,000 cells per cu.mm) as described by Otto (2007). Criteria for SIRS in dogs are given in **Table I**. So to rule of cause of septic SIRS around one ml of blood sample was collected aseptically from jugular vein into EDTA tubes and subjected to polymerase chain reaction (PCR) by using universal 16S rRNA primer and sequencing analysis.

Table 1: Criteria for SIRS in dogs

Temperature	<37.2°C or >39.4°C
Heart Rate (beats/min)	>150/minute
Respiratory Rate (breaths/min)	>40/minute
WBC count (cells/cmm)	<5000 or >19000 >5% bands

The DNA was extracted from blood using DNA extraction kit (QIAamp DNA Blood Mini Kit, Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The DNA isolated

from blood was amplified by PCR using universal primers. Primers used were described in **Table 2**

Table 2: Primers Used

Primers	Sequence(5'-3')	Size of the product
B8F	AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG	1500bp
B1500	AAGGAGGTGATCCAGCCGCA	

A thermal cycling for program with initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 min followed by 35 cycles of denaturation (94°C, 2 min), annealing (58°C, 1 min) and extension (72°C, 1.30 min) and a final extension at 72°C for 7 min was

adopted. The amplicon was electrophoresed in 0.8% agarose gel and the size was resolved using 1Kb DNA ladder (GeNei, Bangalore). Gel extraction of the PCR product was performed using a gel extraction kit (QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The purified PCR product was sequenced using the Applied Biosystem kit. The homology of the PCR product was checked by BLAST analysis against sequences already available in the NCBI GeneBank. The sequences showed 93 per cent homology with the sequences of *Ralstonia* spp. (**Fig.3**).

Fig 1: Open wound on right caudal abdominal region, bruising and ecchymosis of ventral abdominal wall

Fig 2: AFAST identified no free intra-abdominal fluid

Sequences producing significant alignments:

Select: [All](#) [None](#) Selected:0

Alignments Download GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results						
Description	Max score	Total score	Query cover	E value	Ident	Accession
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia sp. strain TCF148 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	150	150	21%	3e-32	93%	MG877653.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia mannitolilytica strain YHBT31 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	150	150	21%	3e-32	93%	MG571736.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia pickettii strain FDAARGOS_410 chromosome 1, complete sequence	150	301	21%	3e-32	93%	CP023537.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia sp. strain S6-9 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	150	150	21%	3e-32	93%	KY357356.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia sp. strain S6-13 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	150	150	21%	3e-32	93%	KY357350.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Ralstonia sp. strain W1-18 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	150	150	21%	3e-32	93%	KY357349.1

Fig 3: Sequencing Results**Results and Discussion:**

Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) is a widespread response to an infectious or a noninfectious insult and, if left untreated, can lead to multiple organ failure and death (de Laforcade, 2015). Sepsis is characterized by a systemic inflammatory response to a bacterial, viral, protozoal or fungal infection. Alterations in the regulation of vasomotor tone, increased vascular permeability, dysfunctional microcirculation, and coagulation abnormalities are hallmarks of sepsis (Boller and Otto, 2015). In this case animal fulfilled three of the SIRS criteria. So to rule of cause of septic SIRS, PCR was performed by using universal 16S rRNA primer. The eluted PCR product was sequenced. The homology of the PCR product was checked by BLAST analysis with the sequences already available in the gene bank and Genus *Ralstonia* septicemia was identified.

Ryan *et al.* (2006) reported that the major conditions associated with *R. pickettii* infection are bacteraemia/septicaemia and respiratory infections/pneumonia and the other conditions including pseudobacteraemia, nosocomial infections, meningitis, osteomyelitis, spondylitis septic arthritis, seminal infection, peritonitis, spinal osteitis, and endocarditis.

Herrera *et al.* (2009) reported a case of *R. pickettii* Septicemia in a dog with Immune-Mediated Thrombocytopenia and the author also stated that the *R. pickettii* should be considered as a cause of bloodstream infections in immunosuppressed veterinary patients. Liu *et al.* (2016) suggested that *R. mannitolilytica*-induced septicemia had an acute disease onset and rapid progression.

In this case, the isolation of genus *Ralstonia* from the blood was unlikely to have been due to contamination because the blood sample was collected aseptically from the jugular vein after the site was shaved and scrubbed. The portal of entry for this patient could be due to an open wound on the right caudal abdominal region, and this genus *Ralstonia* may enter into circulation since the organisms found in moist environments, such as water, soil and plants. The septicemia developed could be due to delayed presentation of patient to the intensive care unit.

Conclusion:

The case presented in this report involves *Ralstonia* spp. induced septicemia in a traumatized dog. This case report emphasises the significance of aseptic procedures to be followed in the hospital, the importance of

immediate presentation of the patient to the hospital, and the significant role of molecular tools in diagnosing the rare causes of septicemia in dogs.

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